

D3.2 Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication Plan v.2

30/09/2025

Abstract

This deliverable presents the updates of WP3 tasks related to exploitation, dissemination and communication activities. It is an updated version of 'D3.1 – Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication Plan v1.0'. Therefore, it details the status and activities of three core tasks on Innovation Management, Communication and Dissemination, and Service Promotion and User Support. The report concludes with future steps for enhancing exploitation, impact, and engagement.

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Work Package 3			
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Executive Summary

This document contains the overall update on the planned tasks related to innovation management, communication and dissemination, service development, user support, engagement, and feedback loop coordination presented in “D3.1 Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication Plan v.1”. The achievements and reviewed plan reflect the work done in the last year of the project under the following tasks: “T3.1 Innovation Management” led by EGI, “T3.3 Communication and Dissemination” led by EGI, and “T3.2 Service promotion, user community support and coordination” led by OpenAIRE.

The first part of the document, with the main contribution from “T3.1: Innovation Management” describes the Innovation Management System (InnoMS) status and updated work plan to structure and run processes for Intellectual Property (IP) assets, and results management, exploitation, sustainability and impact creation.

The second part of the document, with the main contribution from “T3.3: Communication and Dissemination”, provides an update on the activities carried out during the first half of the project, including online presence and events.

The third part consists of activities defined by “T3.2: Service promotion, user community support and coordination” and performed from the first half of the project. The task focuses on the promotion of the EOSC Beyond Core Services with external stakeholders. It showcases the awareness and collaborations with external audiences and among internal partners. Lastly, it presents the creation of informative sessions and resources, reported also via milestones.

Lastly, the document concludes with conclusions and next steps that tie together the three previous sections addressing exploitation, promotion, support and engagement, dissemination and communication.

1. Introduction

To better understand the purpose of this deliverable and how it contributes to the project objectives, this section will summarise the EOSC Beyond objectives and expected results. Moreover, it will provide an overview of the deliverable's structure, its tasks and contributions, and the impact of the deliverable on the overall project.

1.1 The EOSC Beyond project

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is developing as a federation of services, tools, data and other resources from hundreds of providers at local, national, regional and European, to increase discovery, access, and reuse of Open Science resources from European research communities to accelerate discovery times and improve science excellence in Europe.

The EOSC Beyond project aims to support the growth of EOSC in terms of integrated providers and active users by providing new EOSC core technical solutions. Therefore, developers of scientific application environments will be able to compose a diverse portfolio of EOSC resources and offer them to researchers.

Figure 1: The EOSC Core components overview shows new capabilities in blue and improved capabilities in green that will be developed by EOSC Beyond.

To achieve the project's ambition, existing EOSC core solutions are improved, and new core services are added through these Key Exploitable Results (KER):

1. Improved existing EOSC Core services and framework (EB Core Services).
2. EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox with automation tools for testing and validating new EOSC Core services and allowing providers to validate integration with the EOSC Platform before deploying services.

3. EOSC Integration Suite is a portfolio of software adapters to the EOSC Core and horizontal services of the EOSC Exchange.
4. EOSC Execution Framework for composability and deployment of multi-supply resources, which will interoperate with relevant data spaces.
5. EOSC-SIMPL interoperability technical guidelines.
6. Piloting EOSC Thematic and Regional/National Nodes.
7. Sustainability and exploitation plans for the EOSC Core and horizontal services.

Development will be driven by co-design, gathering requirements, and software validation in collaboration with a portfolio of diverse use cases representing the needs of EOSC nodes and initiatives operating at national level (e-Infra CZ in Czechia, NFDI in Germany), regional level (NI4OS in South East Europe), thematic European nodes (CESSDA, CNB-CSIC, ENES, LifeWatch ERIC, METROFood-RI, and Instruct-ERIC), or e-Infra nodes (EGI).

The results of EOSC Beyond will support Open Science for modern data-intensive and multidisciplinary science, enabling scientists, organisations, and countries to discover, access, and reuse an increasing number of resources. As part of the emerging EOSC Federation of Nodes, which officially kicked off with the launch of the EU Node in late 2024, as an integrated operational environment delivering selected horizontal services and the EOSC Core, EOSC Beyond will expand the EOSC Core with additional components and capabilities as an integrated operational environment delivering selected horizontal services and the EOSC Core, Scope and purpose of the deliverable

The scope of the work described in the deliverable is to provide an update on:

- The management and planning of Intellectual Property (IP) and other assets, project results, exploitation and sustainability of Key Exploitable Results (KERs), project impact during the project lifecycle and reporting impact even one year after project conclusion in compliance with Horizon Europe framework requirements.
- The management and planning of communication and dissemination activities during the project's life. As part of these activities, target groups will be informed of the achievements of the project, events will be organised, EOSC brand and EOSC Core services will be promoted, and complementary material will be created to assist in the promotion of the service and user engagement and adoption.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The document is structured in the following way:

- **Section 2** with the main contribution from "T3.1 Innovation Management", describes the Innovation Management System (InnoMS) governance roles and responsibilities, as well as the structure and processes for Intellectual Property (IP) assets, and results management, exploitation and sustainability. It also includes the work plan for the InnoMS implementation.
- **Section 3** with the main contribution from "T3.3 Communication and Dissemination", outlines the target stakeholders for communication and dissemination activities, as well as activities such as defining the visual identity, branding, communication

package and materials, and establishing an online presence including social media. It also features a work plan to carry on the activities described.

- **Section 4** outlines the “T3.2 Service promotion, user community support and coordination” strategy for promoting EOSC Core Services and engaging stakeholders. It focuses on raising awareness, fostering collaborations, and creating learning resources like factsheets, guides, and webinars. These efforts include organising events to onboard new use cases and systematically collecting and analysing feedback to refine materials and services. Crucially, it highlights the internal coordination of feedback loops with WP15 to ensure continuous improvement and effective use case integration, and with WP7 and WP10 to successfully translate new scientific and technical use cases into technical requirements relevant to EOSC Beyond.
- **Section 5** summarises conclusions and next steps that tie together the three previous sections that address work related to exploitation, promotion, support and engagement, dissemination and communication.

1.3 Contributions to the deliverable and outcomes

Different tasks contribute to D3.2, which is used by other tasks as input. This diagram summarises the contribution to the deliverable and how it contributes to other EOSC Beyond tasks.

Figure 2: EOSC Beyond D3.2 inputs and outputs

2. Innovation Management

The EOSC Beyond Innovation Management System (InnoMS) was defined in the previous deliverable “D3.1 Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication Plan v.1.0” as a system with three layers: Governance (Roles and responsibilities), Control (Processes and activities), and Operations (Procedures). Since its design and development was planned in D3.1, this system has been refined to simplify its implementation and align some of its activities with those in WP3. The setup of the InnoMS processes has been completed and is now in the execution stage.

2.1. InnoMS Governance roles and responsibilities

This section contains only the roles and responsibilities that have been refined or added to those already discussed in D3.1.

Role	Tasks	Staff assigned
Project result owner (new)	<p>Project beneficiaries that own results must be identified in accordance with the ‘Grant Agreement section 8. Results’ that perform the following tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure they can fulfil all their obligations under this Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement in relation to Results generated by their employees, personnel or their subcontractors (see Grant Agreement section 8. Results) • Cooperate with the Results Management process manager and provide information as required. E.g. in the template to identify, record, and manage results. compliant with the requirements for the Horizon Europe Mandatory Results Ownership List (ROL) and the ROL table description in Horizon Europe (Horizon) Periodic Report. 	As needed based on the results produced
Process result contact (refined)	<p>Process staff appointed by the WPLG and performs the following tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serve as the primary contact for a project result, encouraging its adoption, exploitation and dissemination. • Support the Results Management process manager in collecting the information related to the results and bridge the gap between technical outputs and their practical implications by promoting uptake. 	1 per result
KER Ambassadors (refined)	<p>Process staff appointed by the WPLG. They perform the following tasks:</p> <p>Tasks at any stage:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serve as the primary representative of a KER, encouraging its adoption, exploitation and dissemination. • Report any issues that threaten the achievement of the KER. 	1 per KER

	<p>Tasks during the development of results contributing to the KER:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn about the expected exploitation, impact creation, and reporting needs for the KER. Their knowledge is backed up by the KER template, which hints at exploitation and reporting needs, and the expected Pathways to impact related to the KER, as well as the Achievement indicators and target values of the Pathway to Impact. • Monitor and observe the activities to achieve results contributing to the KER. • Provide feedback on the activities to produce the results contributing to the KER to ensure alignment with expected exploitation, impact creation and reporting needs. <p>Tasks to develop in parallel or after the results contributing to the KER are available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the KERs Management process manager in collecting the information related to the results and bridge the gap between technical outputs and their practical implications by promoting uptake. 	
Project beneficiary representative for exploitation planning (new)	<p>Process staff identified by the project beneficiaries. They perform the following tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define the exploitation strategy for the project beneficiary they represent. • Support the Exploitation Management process manager in collecting and providing information related to the exploitation strategy for the project beneficiary they represent. 	1 per beneficiary

Table 1: Innovation Management System roles and responsibilities added or refined with respect to D3.1

Processes in InnoMS have been revised and simplified as a result of the project's evolution and task clarification. Additionally, the review resulted in the deletion of the process KER Sustainability Management in order to simplify the collection of sustainability analysis data in the KER partner-specific exploitation plans to be developed within "[Process 4: Exploitation Management¹](#)", which will also simplify the contribution and collaboration with project partners; and due to its overlap with the activities of "T3.4 EOSC Core sustainability". Therefore, InnoMS consists of the five processes depicted in [Figure 1](#).

¹ The link is only available for Consortium members on internal wikipedia.

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Figure 3: EOSC Beyond Innovation Management System processes and their connections

2.2. Work plan update

As part of the work plan update, you will see the status of the process activities (those highlighted in green are completed and those in yellow are work in progress), the timeline, and the staff assigned to produce them.

Process 1: Intellectual Asset Inventory Management (IAIM)	Timeline	Staff assigned
Activity 1: Document process overview and assign roles & responsibilities.	M4 to M5	T3.1/4.1 M.G Ferreiro (EGI)
Activity 2: Create templates and instructions to record Background IP, Third-party IP, Sideground IP and Foreground IP.	M6 to M13	T3.1/4.1A. Pavlidou (OpenAIRE) + Project beneficiaries
Activity 3: Record Background IP, Third-party IP, Sideground IP, and Foreground IP. Iteratively reviewing and updating information and templates as needed. Add link or reference to joint ownership and licensing agreements if provided by project beneficiaries.	M14 to M36	
Process 2: Results Management (RM)	Timeline	Staff assigned
Activity 1: Document process overview and assign roles & responsibilities.	M4 to M5	T3.1/4.1 M.G Ferreiro (EGI)
Activity 2: Define procedure to identify, record, and manage results.	M4 to M8	

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Activity 3: Define a template to identify, record, and manage results. The template will be compliant with the requirements for the Horizon Europe Mandatory Results Ownership List (ROL) .	M6 to M13	T3.1/4.1A. Pavlidou (OpenAIRE) + project contacts for each project result
Activity 4: Make sure a contact person per project result is appointed by the WPLG and provide them with guidelines for successful collaboration.	M13 to M36	
Activity 5: Identify, record and manage results, in addition to iteratively reviewing and updating information and template/s as needed and being compliant with the Horizon Europe Results Ownership List requirements.	M15 to 36	
Process 3: Key Exploitable Results Management (KERM)	Timeline	Staff assigned
Activity 1: Document process overview and assign roles & responsibilities.	M4 to M5	T3.1/4.1 M.G Ferreiro (EGI)
Activity 2: Define procedure and template to identify, record, and manage results.	M4 to M8	+ KER Ambassadors
Activity 3: Identify KERs (assess the KER in the project proposal and add more if necessary) and start filling the KER template.	M9 to M10	
Activity 4: Make sure KER ambassadors are appointed and provide them guidelines for a successful collaboration.	M9 to M12	
Activity 5: Record and manage information about KERs in collaboration with the KERs ambassadors, in addition to iteratively reviewing and updating information, guidelines, and templates as needed.	M13 to M36	
Process 4: Exploitation Management (EM)	Timeline	Staff assigned
Activity 1: Document process overview and assign roles & responsibilities.	M4 to M5	T3.1/4.1 M.G Ferreiro (EGI)
Activity 2: Define high-level exploitation options for project results.	M12 to M13	+ Project beneficiaries
Activity 3: Formulate a methodology, guidelines and a template to create partner-specific KERs exploitation plans.	M12 to M13	
Activity 4: Make sure partner representatives for exploitation planning are appointed and provide them guidelines for a successful collaboration.	M13 to M14	

Activity 5: Support creation of partner-specific KERs exploitation plans, in addition to iteratively reviewing and updating information and templates as needed.	M15 to M36	T3.1/4.1A. Pavlidou (OpenAIRE) + Project partner representative for exploitation planning
Activity 6: Establish collaboration channels with other EOSC projects, the EOSC Association, and the procurement consortia to identify exploitation opportunities.	M4 to M36	T3.1/4.1 M.G Ferreiro (EGI) T3.3/4.3 F. Drago (EGI)
Activity 7: Investigate collaboration and exploitation options for project results through the EOSC DIH.	M4 to M36	T3.1/4.1 E. Cauhé (EGI)
Process 5: Impact Management (IM)	Timeline	Staff assigned
Activity 1: Document process overview and assign roles & responsibilities.	M4 to M5	T3.1/4.1 M.G Ferreiro (EGI)
Activity 2: Define the pathways to impact according to the impact canvas report.	M11 to M13	+ Project Manager + Comms Manager
Activity 3: Continually update the impact canvas pathway and report required in collaboration with beneficiaries.	M14 to M36	+ Project beneficiaries
Activity 4: Facilitate collecting information for the final reporting on the project's impact according to Horizon Europe (Horizon) Periodic Report in collaboration with the Project Management Office.	M34 to M36	

Table 2: T3.1 workplan update

2.3. Procedures update

The procedure “**PROC05 Results monitoring for exploitation**”² in the operational layer has been updated to allow KER ambassadors and project result owners to formally report any issues that could jeopardize a KER.

2.4. Additional tasks

A vocabulary was created (on the internal, project Confluence space) to facilitate the use of the InnoMS as well as an Innovation Management video and slides for all project beneficiaries to understand the importance and contractual obligations of maximising the project's impact. That action also assists the project partners to find definitions of terms related to innovation, IPs, impact and exploitation, available on EC portals.

² The link is only available for Consortium members on internal wikipedia.

3. Communication and Dissemination

This section primarily covers activities related to Task 3.3 Communication and Dissemination, as well as its collaboration with Task 3.2 “Service Promotion, User Community Support, and Coordination”, in support of other tasks and Work Packages (WPs) across EOSC Beyond.

3.1. Communication and dissemination activities

In this section, we provide relevant updates since D3.1 (M6) and the envisioned next steps concerning the project’s external communication and dissemination activities.

3.1.1. Online presence

The EOSC Beyond website was launched in M1 (April 2024) and initially expanded in M4 (July 24) as requested by Milestone MS4 (see D3.1). Since then, the following new pages and sections have been created:

Main page	Children pages	Comment
Pilots https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/pilots	e-INFRA CZ EGI Instruct-ERIC LifeWatch ERIC METROFOOD-RI NFDI NI4OS CESSDA CNB-CSIC ENES	A dedicated page with a brief description of each Pilot node.
Resources https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/resources-outputs	Project Deliverables https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/project-deliverables	This section serves as a gateway to explore the tangible outcomes of our project, designed to support researchers, innovators, and stakeholders in leveraging our services. In particular, the Project Deliverables page features an automatic integration with Zenodo, showcasing materials from our Zenodo community directly on the project website. This was implemented in Dec 2024, M10.

Table 3: New pages and sections created since M4

News and events have been constantly updated on the website, reflecting the evolution of the project and our participation in events.

3.1.1.1. Social media

LinkedIn remains the primary social media channel for EOSC Beyond³, offering a professional platform to share project updates, engage with stakeholders, and foster a

³ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eosc-beyond/>

growing community of followers. YouTube⁴ hosts multimedia content such as video interviews, webinar recordings, tutorials, and other educational materials.

The main update related to social media was the launch of the EOSC Beyond Bluesky channel in M9⁵, pioneering a move that was then followed by many other EOSC-related and Horizon Europe projects.

Figure 4: Promotional image for EOSC Beyond Bluesky account launch.

3.1.1.2. Newsletter

The first issue of the EOSC Beyond quarterly newsletter was distributed at the end of M3, featuring comprehensive updates on KERs, project milestones, upcoming events, and community opportunities. All other issues were successfully sent following the schedule and added to the website for future reference⁶.

3.1.2. Collaborations and Events

3.1.2.1. Collaborating with the EOSC community

EOSC Beyond representatives routinely participated in the collaboration groups facilitated by the EOSC Focus project (followed up by EOSC Gravity in M15), as well as in key invitation-only meetings, such as the EOSC Winter School and the annual Coordination meetings of EOSC-related projects funded under Horizon Europe, organised by the European Commission in June 2024 and 2025.

An exemplary outcome of this work was the publication of the EOSC Beyond Concept Paper on the EOSC Federation Architecture and Federating Capabilities⁷ in October 2024, reaching

⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/@EOSCBeyond>

⁵ <https://bsky.app/profile/eosc-beyond.bsky.social>

⁶ <https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/eosc-beyond-newsletter>

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13939396>

over 1800 downloads on Zenodo as of the end of M17 and contributing to the following version of the EOSC Federation Handbook⁸.

Figure 5: Promotion image for the concept paper.

3.1.2.2. Webinars

EOSC Beyond hosted the first public webinar⁹ on 19 June 2025 to introduce the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox to the wider EOSC community. The webinar featured a presentation of the Innovation Sandbox by Technical Coordinator Nicola Fiore (EGI Foundation), as well as lightning talks by three pilot nodes (ENES, NFDI, and CESSDA), inviting external stakeholders to visit the Sandbox and get in touch with the team.

The webinar welcomed 93 registrants and 46 unique viewers, and it brought 56 new subscribers to the quarterly newsletter. The recording and slides were made available the day after via the project YouTube channel and the Zenodo community.

We plan to host more webinars through the second half of the project, showcasing the evolution of the Sandbox and the other key exploitable results to the wider EOSC community.

⁸ <https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/article/first-edition-eosc-federation-handbook-released>

⁹ <https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/event/webinar-eosc-core-innovation-sandbox>

Figure 6: Promotional image for the first EOSC Beyond webinar.

3.1.2.3. Third-party events

EOSC Beyond is actively participating in key third-party events to showcase the project's progress and engage with the broader scientific and research community. The project's involvement included delivering presentations, presenting posters and demonstrations, taking on speaking roles, and hosting booths at exhibitions.

EOSC Beyond representatives successfully participated in key events such as the EOSC Symposium 2024¹⁰, EGI2024¹¹ and EGI2025¹² held by EGI, TNC25¹³ organised by GÉANT, the EUDAT Conference 2024¹⁴, and the OSFAIR 2025¹⁵ hosted by OpenAIRE.

In addition to these public events, the EOSC Beyond team also participated in several community-specific events, such as the 3rd Symposium on Open Science in Greece¹⁶ and the METROFOOD Open Event¹⁷ in December 2024, as well as the LifeWatch BEES Conference¹⁸ in July 2025.

¹⁰ <https://eosc.eu/symposium2024/>

¹¹ <https://www.egi.eu/event/egi2024/>

¹² <https://www.egi.eu/event/egi2025/>

¹³ <https://eudat.eu/events/third-party-event/tnc25>

¹⁴ <https://eudat.eu/events/conferences/eudat-conference-2024>

¹⁵ <https://www.opensciencefair.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://www.hellenicopenscience.gr/en/events-en/conferences-en/3rd-greek-oss-en>

¹⁷ <https://www.egi.eu/event/metrofood-epi-open-event/>

¹⁸ <https://www.lifewatch.eu/bees-2025/>

3.1.3. KPIs

EOSC Beyond is generally on track with its M36 communication and dissemination targets, we are expecting to meet some of them even before M36.

Item	August 2025 (M17)	Target value (M36)
Monthly website visits	397	300
Newsletter	5 issues	12
Subscribers	151	300
Average open rate	52%	35%
LinkedIn		
Followers	568	1000
Monthly impressions	2985	3500
Monthly engagement rate	10.1	6.5
YouTube		
Total views	370	700
Bluesky		
Followers	214	250
Third-party events		
Presentations, panels, posters, demonstrations, booths	16	20

Table 4: Communications KPIs

3.2. Work plan update

The table below shows the status of the activities work plan of task 3.2.

Activity	Timeline	Owner	Status
Activity 1: Provide a visual identity and ensure it remains consistent throughout the project Production of logo and brand manual - oversee the creation of new materials for consistency.	M3 (Jun-24)	Federico Drago, EGI Foundation	Completed
Activity 2: Provide the basic communication package and materials Creation of general materials for the project and inclusion on Confluence	M3 (Jun-24)	Federico Drago, EGI Foundation	Completed
Activity 3: Create and maintain project website It was launched in M1 and was expanded to include key project information such as partners, services, news and events by M4 (Jul-24) as requested by MS4. New content is created when needed.	M1 (Apr-24) -M36 (Mar-27)	Federico Drago, EGI Foundation	On time
Activity 4: Set up and manage social media	M1 (Apr-24) -M36	Federico Drago, EGI Foundation	On time

Activity	Timeline	Owner	Status
presence Setup and management of LinkedIn and YouTube channels. Bluesky added in M9.	(Mar-27)		
Activity 5: Create and manage quarterly project newsletter Maintain newsletter subscriber community on Mailerlite, produce and send quarterly newsletters starting in June 2024. 6 newsletters were sent on schedule as of M17	M3 (Jun-24) -M36 (Mar-27)	Federico Drago, EGI Foundation	On time
Activity 6: Contribute to relevant deliverables Draft together with T3.1, T3.2 and other relevant tasks the exploitation, dissemination and communication deliverables D3.1 and D3.2.	3M4 (Jul-24)-M6 (Sep-24) M16 (Jul-25) - M18 (Sep-25)	Federico Drago, EGI Foundation Androniki Pavlidou, Maja Dolinar, OpenAIRE Andre Vieira, UMINHO (OpenAIRE)	Completed
Activity 7: Production of Promotional material of EOSC Core services This includes eBooks, Slide decks, videos, to be created in collaboration with T3.2 and relevant partners.	M6 (Sep-24)-M36	Androniki Pavlidou, OpenAIRE Andre Vieira, UMINHO (OpenAIRE)	On time MS5 - Completed MS6 - to be completed at M36)
Activity 8: Facilitating project workshops and supporting presence at third-party events Especially related to the MS7 “Promotion of 7 support activities per communities/stakeholder”, in collaboration with T3.2 and relevant partners.	M1 (Apr-24) - M36 (Mar-27)	Androniki Pavlidou, OpenAIRE Maja Dolinar, OpenAIRE Federico Drago, EGI Foundation	In progress
Activity 9: Collaboration with Horizon Europe EOSC Projects on comms Participation in monthly meetings and activities with other comms representatives from Horizon Europe EOSC Projects.	M1 (Apr-24) - M36 (Mar-27)	Federico Drago, EGI Foundation	In progress
Activity 10: Monitoring and reporting of activities Ensure communication and dissemination KPIs and activities are monitored every month via the dedicated channels. Contribute to official progress reports.	M1 (Apr-24) - M36 (Mar-27)	Federico Drago, EGI Foundation Androniki Pavlidou, OpenAIRE	On time

Table 5 - Formal activity Breakdown

4. Service promotion, user community support and feedback loop coordination

Section 4 outlines the activities to promote the EOSC Beyond Core Services, support user communities, and coordinate feedback loops with other technical work packages. The task focuses on showcasing the value of EOSC Core services—namely the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox, the EOSC Execution Framework, and the EOSC Integration Suite—through dedicated promotional and training materials, including eBooks and slide decks. These materials were disseminated via the project website and social media channels, contributing to the achievement of Milestone MS5. Task 3.2 also engaged proactively with lead users and the broader research community through participation in 11 major events, including the EOSC Symposium, EGI Conference, and WP15 workshops. Internally, coordination workshops with WP7–WP9 and WP15 facilitated alignment between user needs and technical development. Feedback gathered through these engagements is instrumental for informing ongoing developments in WP10, WP11, WP13, and WP15.

4.1. Service promotion and user community support activities

Task 3.2 has made substantial progress in promoting EOSC Beyond services, engaging diverse user communities, and facilitating internal and external feedback loops. The task delivered key milestones, established a robust engagement strategy, and provided reusable outreach materials supporting the wider dissemination and adoption of EOSC Core services.

4.1.1. Development of promotional and training materials

A central component of Task 3.2 has been the development of high-quality promotional and training materials designed to raise awareness of EOSC Beyond Core services and support user onboarding. As part of this effort, templates for **eBooks** and **slide decks** were developed in alignment with the project’s visual identity and branding guidelines. These templates were populated with content for each of the three key EOSC Beyond Core services: the **EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox**, the **EOSC Execution Framework**, and the **EOSC Integration Suite**. These efforts led to the timely achievement of **Milestone MS5: Promotional material of EOSC Core services**, delivered in March 2025.

The materials were published both on the [EOSC Beyond project website](#) and in the project’s dedicated [Zenodo community](#), ensuring they are publicly accessible, citable, and preserved in the long term. The “Project Deliverables” section of the website serves as a central access point to these materials and showcases key documentation that reflects the project’s contributions to EOSC. This multi-channel publication strategy supports wide dissemination and easy discoverability of the outputs.

To support diverse stakeholder needs, the materials were made available in two formats: eBooks (as pdf files) and slide decks (as pdf files). Each format presents the services in a

clear, user-friendly language that is suitable for researchers, service providers, and technical developers alike. The eBooks offer in-depth narrative content and guidance on how to leverage the services, while the slide decks provide concise, visually engaging summaries suitable for presentations, workshops, and training sessions.

Each EOSC Core service is introduced with a clear purpose and value proposition:

- The **EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox** allows users to *test, validate, and innovate* by providing a comprehensive testbed equipped with advanced automation tools. These tools support the testing and validation of new EOSC services in a pre-production environment, helping developers ensure integration readiness.
- The **EOSC Execution Framework** enables users to *deploy, access, and scale* their resources. It offers a composability-based suite of applications that streamline service deployment and enhance accessibility across the EOSC ecosystem.
- The **EOSC Integration Suite** is designed to *share, reuse, and collaborate*. It provides a curated set of software adapters and integration patterns that help research communities and technology providers achieve interoperability between their tools and EOSC Core services.

Since publication, these materials have shown promising levels of engagement. As of September 2025, the **EOSC Beyond Integration Suite eBook** has been viewed 115 times and downloaded 109 times, while the **EOSC Beyond Core Innovation Sandbox eBook** recorded 63 views and 83 downloads. The EOSC Beyond **Execution Framework eBook** followed closely with 57 views and 51 downloads. Slide decks also performed well: the EOSC Beyond **Integration Suite** slide deck had 42 views and 42 downloads, EOSC Beyond **Innovation Sandbox** slide deck reached the values of 60 views and 51 downloads, and lastly the EOSC Beyond **Execution Framework** slide deck follows with 28 views and 31 downloads.

Together, these promotional and training materials play a vital role in equipping current and potential users with the necessary understanding to adopt and work with EOSC Beyond services. They also serve as key communication assets during events, webinars, and training workshops—providing a foundation for broader community engagement and feedback collection efforts across EOSC Beyond.

4.1.2. Supportive Training Resources

As part of the broader effort to enhance service promotion and user engagement, Task 3.2 integrated a range of supportive training resources into its outreach and onboarding strategy. The development of these materials was informed by established good practices drawn from prior EOSC-related projects, including OpenAIRE-Nexus, Blue-Cloud, and FAIRCORE4EOSC. These projects served as valuable references, offering tested approaches for training content design, format, and delivery.

In Activities 1 through 5, partners collaboratively reviewed exemplary resources such as the OpenAIRE-Nexus ARGOS training materials, OpenAIRE factsheets, OpenAIRE guides, OpenPlato courses, and a variety of tutorial videos and demos from Blue-Cloud's Training Academy and FAIRCORE4EOSC. These references helped define content structures, tone,

and visual presentation styles that would be adopted for EOSC Beyond’s materials. The result was a well-grounded foundation for the project’s own eBooks, factsheets, guides, tutorials, and pitch decks, tailored specifically to the features and user benefits of the EOSC Core services.

To ensure consistency, templates for each type of resource were created and aligned with the project’s brand identity. These templates enabled efficient collaboration across partners and allowed for modular updates as services evolved. The content was designed to be both informative and accessible: *factsheets* serve as portable, visually engaging summaries for use at events and presentations; *guides* provide step-by-step onboarding and usage instructions hosted on web pages; and *tutorials*—including short videos—support hands-on learning and can be embedded within guides or distributed independently.

As of September 2025, **the development of factsheets and updates to guides and tutorials is ongoing** (Activity 10). These updates are necessary to reflect the evolving user interface (UI) and user experience (UX) of the EOSC Beyond services, as well as new technical features introduced by WP7, WP10, and WP15. To ensure quality and usability, new materials are reviewed internally by task contributors and partners, before being published.

To effectively plan the development of these materials, the progress made by the technical work packages is being considered to ensure alignment with the service delivery timelines. Therefore, we plan to deliver the materials as soon as the services are made available. Since the factsheets provide an overview of the services, they will be delivered first. Afterwards, we will produce the tutorials and guides according to the following timeline.

Service	Factsheets	Tutorials	Guides
EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox	September 2025	November - December 2025	January - May 2026
EOSC Execution Framework	October 2025	November - December 2025	January - May 2026
EOSC Integration Suite	October 2025	November - December 2025	January - May 2026

Table 6: Timeline to develop Supportive Training Resources

These materials will be continuously updated as needed, in line with any updates to the services.

As with ebooks and slide decks, the factsheets template was created. A preview of the template is in the image below.

Figure 7: Template for the Services Factsheets

Templates and production guidelines have also been defined for the tutorials and guides. The guides will follow the structure:

- What it is;
- What it does;
- Getting started [if applicable];
- How can I use it;
- Technical Requirements [if applicable];
- Support;
- More Information.

The instructions for tutorials include detailed guidelines on how to create them, covering aspects such as recommended sections, length, technical details, and more.

These supportive training resources are an essential component of EOSC Beyond’s capacity-building and adoption strategy. They not only empower users to navigate the services with confidence but also play a key role in outreach to new communities, contributing to broader uptake and sustainability of the EOSC Core.

4.1.3. Community Engagement

A core objective of Task 3.2 has been to ensure widespread visibility of EOSC Beyond services and foster engagement with diverse user communities through active participation in strategic events and internal workshops. These activities have been crucial for

disseminating project results, gathering user feedback, building synergies with other EOSC-related initiatives, and supporting the broader uptake of the EOSC Core services.

Between April 2024 and September 2025, EOSC Beyond was presented at **11 major international and European events**, ranging from large-scale conferences and symposia to targeted stakeholder meetings. Notable highlights include participation in the [EOSC Symposium 2024](#) (21 - 23 October 2024, Berlin, Germany), [EGI2024](#) (30 September - 4 October 2024, Lecce, Italy), the [EUDAT Conference](#) (3 - 5 December 2024, Karlsruhe, Germany) and [EGI2025](#) (2-6 June, Santander, Spain). These appearances positioned EOSC Beyond prominently within the European and global Open Science landscape. EOSC Beyond has successfully contributed to the [Open Science FAIR 2025](#) (September 2025, Geneva, Switzerland), where it highlighted its role in supporting the development and long-term sustainability of federated and national infrastructures within the EOSC ecosystem.

At these venues, EOSC Beyond partners delivered presentations, joined high-level panel discussions, hosted collaborative workshops, and shared materials showcasing the value and functionalities of the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox, Execution Framework, and Integration Suite. For example, during the “EOSC Federation – Interoperability” session at the EOSC Symposium 2024, EOSC Beyond contributed insights on aligning services with federation capabilities. Similarly, at EGI2024, the project co-organised a session titled “*Empowering Open Science: EGI Community’s Impact on EOSC*,” which consolidated its role in the e-Infrastructure community.

Additionally, EOSC Beyond was featured at thematic and strategic meetings such as the EOSC Tripartite Meeting (June 2024), [DISCOVER-US Vision Workshop](#) (June 2024), and the [METROFOOD Open Event](#) (December 2024), enabling cross-disciplinary outreach and collaboration across sectors like agrifood systems and distributed computing. These events served not only to communicate project results but also to position EOSC Beyond services within the wider EOSC ecosystem and related European research infrastructures.

The project also maintained strong involvement in internal EOSC coordination meetings, including the 2024 and 2025 EOSC Projects Coordination Meetings in Brussels and regular EOSC EU Node discussions. These engagements ensured alignment with the broader strategic development of the EOSC EU Node and promoted collaboration between Horizon Europe-funded EOSC projects.

In parallel to external dissemination, internal coordination was strengthened through a series of three major project workshops, which helped align technical development with user requirements and feedback:

1. **Technical Workshop – Athens (November 2024)**: Hosted in person, this workshop gathered 22 project partners to discuss technical integration challenges and early service deployment insights.
2. **Pilots Workshop – December 2024 (WP8-led)**: A focused session that brought together another 22 participants to refine pilot use cases and share lessons learned during initial testing phases.

3. **Pilots & Technical Support Workshop – Krakow (March 2025):** Organised by AGH-UST in collaboration with WP15, this hybrid-format workshop attracted 36 participants and focused on aligning pilot user stories with service development—particularly addressing interoperability and composability requirements.

The collective impact of these events has been significant in terms of building community awareness, testing EOSC Beyond’s messaging and materials, and ensuring real-world relevance of services through stakeholder engagement. All activities have been logged in the project’s dissemination records and reported to the European Commission via the official portal, reflecting the project’s commitment to transparent and impactful communication.

The following table lists the dissemination activities to engage external audiences via participation to events, along with the type of dissemination material used. Of course, there are more engagement and informative activities taken via networking and participation to the events mentioned beforehand.

Year/Month	Title and Event	Type of Material	Partner
2025/June	EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox ¹⁹ EGI2025	Poster	Federico Drago (EGI), Maja Dolinar (OpenAIRE)
2025/June	The ENES Pilot Node: Exploring the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox ²⁰ EOSC Beyond Webinar	Demo	Antonio Fabrizio (ENES)
2025/June	CESSDA Pilot Node ²¹ EOSC Beyond Webinar	Presentation	John Shepherdson (CESSDA ERIC)
2025/June	The NFDI Pilot Node & the EB Sandbox ²² EOSC Beyond Webinar	Presentation	Tim Wetzel (DESY), Jos van Wezel (KIT), Sander Apweiler, Marvin Winkens (FZJ), York Sure-Vetter (NFDI)
2025/June	EOSC Beyond Intro and Deep Dive into the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox ²³ EOSC Beyond Webinar	Presentation	Nicola Fiore (EGI)

Table 7: Dissemination and engagement activities

Moving forward, the project will maintain its active presence in strategic forums, with planned participation in the **EOSC Symposium 2025** in Brussels and other key events. These engagements will further reinforce EOSC Beyond’s contribution to shaping the future of EOSC services, interoperability, and community-driven innovation.

Another impact of the engagement and dissemination activities is also the “Internal/External communities contributing to co-design”, which is also an impact indicator of the project. By

¹⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/15624915>

²⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/15703656>

²¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/15703486>

²² <https://zenodo.org/records/15703051>

²³ <https://zenodo.org/records/15703410>

participating to related events where many diverse communities join, the project has already overcome its target value of #5 as reported by other WPs (already #13 co-design activities via the communities connected to the Pilot Nodes).

#	Year/ Month	Activity Event	Target community	Partner(s) involved)
1	2025/June	<u>EOSC - Services and Technologies for EOSC</u> with focus on sustainability of <u>EOSC Core Services</u> , EGI 2025 Conference	EOSC Core services providers, Policy makers, Funders	Dale Robertson, Mark Dietrich (EGI) Amanda Calatrava (UPV) Thanassis Mantes (ARC) Androniki Pavlidou (OpenAIRE)
2	2025/June	<u>Software Quality Assurance and Release Management for EOSC Beyond</u>	Developers, Software engineers communities	John Shepherdson (CESSDA)
3	2025/June	“EOSC - Nodes for the build-up” <u>Takeaways from the NFDI pilot node preparation in EOSC Beyond</u> <u>EOSC Beyond: The CESSDA Pilot Node</u> <u>Driving the Evolution of EOSC: The Role of EOSC Beyond in the establishment of the EOSC Federation Infrastructures</u>	EOSC Nodes Communities, Developers EOSC Nodes Communities EOSC Community	Tim Wetzel (DESY) John Shepherdson (CESSDA) Nicola Fiore (EGI)
4	2025/Sept.	Digital Rights Vocabulary for EOSC <u>Introducing OpenREL: Rights Expression Languages for Open Science and International Data Spaces – A Practitioners’ Approach</u> OSFAIR 2025	Workshop with the community to collect feedback	Melios Katsamakias, Prodromos Tsiavos (OpenAIRE) Wim Hugo (DANS KNAW)
5	2025/Sept.-Nov.	EOSC Symposium 2025	Planned and waiting for approval	Will be based on which submissions will be accepted.

Table 8: Co-design activities, as impact indicators, related with WP3

4.1.4. Liaison and Coordination Activities

A key element of Task 3.2 has been the establishment and maintenance of strong liaison and coordination activities with other EOSC-related initiatives, particularly projects funded

under the HORIZON-INFRA-2023 call. These efforts are instrumental in ensuring alignment with broader EOSC developments, facilitating the reuse of resources, and fostering a coherent approach across the evolving EOSC ecosystem.

Through Activity 9, EOSC Beyond has maintained regular collaboration with peer projects via joint workshops, coordination meetings, and monthly communication exchanges—many of which are facilitated by EOSC Focus and other coordination mechanisms. These interactions provide a platform for sharing good practices, identifying complementary activities, and aligning messaging, particularly around the EOSC Core services and their implementation within the broader EOSC Federation architecture. As the EOSC EU Node and other national or thematic nodes mature, this coordination is essential to avoid fragmentation, enhance service integration, and promote long-term sustainability through shared approaches.

Building on this foundation, EOSC Beyond will expand its engagement efforts by actively cooperating with two newly launched projects: [EOSC United](#) and [EOSC Gravity](#). These initiatives will play a central role in shaping the next phase of the EOSC ecosystem, particularly in supporting the maturity and cohesion of the EOSC Federation.

EOSC United is a Coordination and Support Action dedicated to fostering an inclusive engagement model for the EOSC Federation. With the EOSC EU Node now operational as of autumn 2024, EOSC United serves as a key factor in mobilising research communities around FAIR data and services across disciplines and borders. The project contributes to the evolution of the EOSC EU Node by collecting feedback, promoting the uptake of federated services, and showcasing adoption through curated use cases in collaboration with EOSC GRAVITY. EOSC Beyond will support these efforts by ensuring alignment of technical developments, reinforcing the messaging around EOSC Core services, and contributing to the co-design of user engagement pathways based on its existing experience in stakeholder liaison and onboarding.

EOSC Gravity will further consolidate the coordination and sustainability of the EOSC ecosystem. As the successor to EOSC Focus, it will facilitate the transition of the EOSC Partnership into a future governance and funding framework beyond 2027. EOSC Beyond will contribute to this process by engaging in inter-project collaborations, providing inputs into the revision of the SRIA 2.0, and exchanging knowledge to support the establishment of new EOSC Nodes through funding mechanisms introduced by GRAVITY's open calls.

Through joint activities, knowledge sharing, and coordinated stakeholder engagement, EOSC Beyond, EOSC United, and EOSC Gravity will collectively strengthen the implementation and long-term resilience of the EOSC Federation. This strategic alignment will help realise a seamless, federated research infrastructure that supports open, interdisciplinary, and impactful science across Europe.

In parallel, Activity 6 focused on the systematic identification of opportunities for user engagement and targeted stakeholder outreach. A curated list of relevant conferences, workshops, and community events was compiled and is continuously updated on the project's internal Confluence space. This list serves as a strategic planning tool for both Task 3.2 and Task 3.3, guiding the selection of dissemination venues and shaping the project's

external presence. Importantly, it also includes targeted stakeholder categories—such as research communities, infrastructure providers, policy makers, and thematic service developers—ensuring that outreach is both focused and relevant to the audiences EOSC Beyond aims to support.

Together, these liaison and coordination activities strengthen the project’s integration into the wider EOSC landscape, amplify the visibility of its services, and contribute to a more interoperable and collaborative European Open Science environment. As the project progresses into its second phase, these connections will continue to be leveraged to co-design services, share materials, and align engagement strategies with the evolving needs of the research community.

4.2. Workplan update

Task 3.3 updated work plan follows below, with status and more information.

Activity	Timeline	Owner	Status
<p>Activity 1: Suggest good practices of material - eBooks, Pitch Decks adopted by OpenAIRE-Nexus H2020 funded project</p> <p>Follow the same narrative that could be adjusted to the needs of the project and EOSC Core services.</p>	M4 (Jul-24)	Androniki Pavlidou, OpenAIRE	Completed
<p>Activity 2: Suggest good practices of training material - Factsheets, Guides, Tutorials, for the EOSC Core services</p> <p>Creation of a list of material that could be useful as good practices out of experience with H2020 projects and users’ requirements, feedback</p>	M3 (Jun-24)	Andre Vieira, Pedro Príncipe /OpenAIRE-UMI NHO Federico Drago, EGI Foundation	Completed
<p>Activity 3: Templates of eBook, Pitch Decks (Slide decks) available for review and final version, for the EOSC Core services.</p> <p>Creation of the templates that would be used later for services and would be disseminated through the communication and dissemination channels. The structure of the information should be clear.</p>	M4 (Jul-24)-M7 (Oct-24)	Androniki Pavlidou, OpenAIRE	Completed
<p>Activity 4: Prepare EOSC Core services and Pilots promotion, user engagement and liaison activities</p> <p>Suggest activities with high impact, value, and user engagement. Suggest activities among the other EOSC related projects.</p>	M3 (Jun-24) - M6 (Sep-24)	Maja Dolinar, OpenAIRE	Completed

<p>Activity 5: Prepare templates of support materials for the EOSC Core services, i.e. factsheets, guides, tutorials, posters</p> <p>Material should be made easy to comprehend and downloadable via the project website. Could be updated as services evolve. Factsheets are mainly portable PDF documents that can be accessed online but can be used at in-person events; the guides are essentially web pages with basic information on the service (What it is, What it does, How can I use it?, Technical Requirements); and the tutorials are short videos that can be embedded in guides or made available individually on a video channel.</p>	M4 (Jul-24)-M8 (Nov-24)	Andre Vieira, Pedro Príncipe /OpenAIRE-UMI NHO	Completed
<p>Activity 6: Create a list of events, workshops to attend as part of T3.3 and T3.2 user engagement activities. Name the targeted groups of stakeholders.</p> <p>The list can include suggested events by the consortium.</p>	M4 (Jul-24)-M6 (Sep-24)	Maja Dolinar, OpenAIRE Federico Drago, EGI Foundation	Completed
<p>Activity 7: Deliver eBooks, Pitch decks (slide decks) of the EOSC Core services (Milestone MS5)</p> <p>Provide the finalised templates with information on the new EOSC Core services of the project.</p>	M12 (Mar-25)	Androniki Pavlidou, OpenAIRE	Completed
<p>Activity 8: Publish eBooks, Pitch decks on website (T3.2 ted) and update the files when the EOSC Core services develop</p> <p>Ongoing process, that should be communicated via Task 3.3 to inform users.</p>	M12 (Mar-25)-M36 (Mar-27)	Federico Drago, EGI Foundation Androniki Pavlidou, OpenAIRE	Completed
<p>Activity 9: Liaison among HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC projects and other EOSC related funded projects</p> <p>Promote project value, through its services, pilots, outcomes, and receive feedback.</p>	M6 (Sep-24)-M36 (Mar-27)	Maja Dolinar, OpenAIRE	Ongoing
<p>Activity 10: Delivery of supportive material of EOSC Core services; factsheets, guides, tutorials, and update the files when services develop, new UX, UI issues are fixed</p> <p>Material should be clear to users, comprehensive, and memorable to users, made available via a multi-channel approach. The templates will be also reviewed by the consortium.</p>	M14 (May-25) - M36 (Mar-27)	Andre Vieira, Pedro Príncipe /OpenAIRE-UMI NHO	In progress
<p>Activity 11: Publish supportive material of EOSC Core services of activity 10 on project website</p> <p>Allow users to find the information and download it.</p>	M14 (May-25) -	Federico Drago, EGI Foundation	In progress

D3.2 Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication Plan v.2

	M36 (Mar-27)		
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Table 9: Work plan of Task 3.2

5. Conclusions and next steps

During the first half of the project, T3.1 Innovation Management established a clear governance structure that facilitates understanding of roles and responsibilities, the processes and activities to implement innovation management, as well as the procedures to follow step-by-step instructions and start the operational work. In the second half of the project, as part of T4.1, the management of IP assets, results, exploitation of KERs, sustainability, and impact will continue. Every six months, project reports will provide regular updates on task progress. When the end of the activities is reached, a 'D4.1 IP Management and Exploitation Report' will be produced documenting the project's intellectual property management and exploitation activities.

T3.3 has accomplished the first half of the project, giving visibility to early outputs such as the concept paper and the launch of the Innovation Sandbox for external stakeholders. EOSC Beyond is well-positioned within the wider EOSC community and actively contributes to key meetings and events. In the second half of the project, we expect to further increase public activities and support T3.2 towards the dissemination of its outputs. Results will be showcased in MS8.

Regarding T3.2, focus would be given to update the established materials, create new ones (factsheets, guides) and proactively as services evolve, to inform all stakeholders on EOSC Beyond services. Driven by T3.1, Intellectual Properties would be added gradually within the related material of T3.2 and be promoted via the Communication and Dissemination activities of T3.3.

Acronyms

Term	Definition
DoA	Description of Activities
EOSC-A	EOSC Association
EOSC-A TFs	EOSC Association Task Forces
EB Core Services	Core services being developed by EOSC Beyond
EOSC DIH	EOSC Digital Innovation Hub
EOSC SB	EOSC Steering Board
Exploitation Management (EM) process	This process defines an exploitation methodology that can be used by project partners to create their exploitation plans, especially for Key Exploitable Results. In this process, exploitation opportunities are identified that can be pursued during or after the project to increase its impact. Exploitation activities can include commercial exploitation, developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing products and processes, providing services, or standardising.
Impact Management (IM) process	This process records information that will be used to assess the impact of the project in accordance with Horizon Europe recommendations. Impact is considered from three complementary perspectives: scientific, societal and economic. These different views are recorded in pathways to impact and a brief impact canvas report.
Innovation Management System (InnoMS)	Management System for the Innovation activities within EOSC Beyond.
Intellectual Asset Inventory Management (IAIM) process	This process records and manages IP that existed before the project started (relevant to the execution and exploitation of the project and called Background IP) as well as IP generated during the project (which includes Sideground, Third-Party and Foreground IP).
Intellectual Property (IP)	Unique, value-adding creations of the human intellect that result from human ingenuity, creativity and inventiveness. source: ISO 56005:2020
Key Exploitable Result (KER)	An identified main interesting result, which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.

	source: Horizon Europe Results Platform publication on Making Results Matter
KERs Management (KERM) process	This process records and manages all the information related to Key Exploitable Results, results which have a high potential for exploitation.
KERs Sustainability Management (SM) process	This process defines a sustainability analysis methodology that can be used by the project partners to create their sustainability plans, especially for KERs. It also identifies sustainability opportunities that can be pursued during or after the project to increase its impact. For example by analysing potential funding opportunities, considering the work of the EOSC SB, EOSC-A TFs, EOSC projects, analysing data on user experience and the EOSC's value proposition. Finally, this process will provide support for analysing legal and regulatory barriers and developing recommendations for minimising or avoiding them.
MS	Milestone
Results Management (RM) process	This process records and manages all the results generated during the project duration. The results of a project may include tangible or intangible effects of the project, such as data, know-how, algorithms, prototypes, new products or services, roadmaps, policy recommendations, lessons learned, reports, publications, and other information, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to them, including intellectual property rights.
SIMPL	Open source, smart and secure middleware platform that supports data access and interoperability among European data spaces. source: Simpl: Cloud-to-edge federations empowering EU data spaces
TCB	Technical Coordination Board
WP	Work Package
WPLG	Work Package Leader Group at EOSC Beyond

Table 10: Acronyms